

Synchronous Primary Endometrial and Ovarian Cancers: Pathogenesis, Treatment and Prognosis

Editorial

Androutsopoulos G^{1*}, Decavalas G¹¹Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, University of Patras, Medical School, Rion, Greece.***Corresponding Author:**

Georgios Androutsopoulos MD,
Lecturer, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology,
University of Patras, Medical School,
Rion 26504, Greece.
Tel: +306974088092
E-mail: androutsopoulos@upatras.gr

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Synchronous primary cancers are relatively uncommon in general population.[1] Only 0.5-1.7% of women with gynecological malignancies, have synchronous primary cancers of the female genital tract.[2-6] Among them, the most common combination is synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers.[2,3,5]

The pathogenesis of synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers, remains unclear[5,7] The theory of the secondary Müllerian system has been proposed to explain the development of multiple primary cancers of the female genital tract.[5-9] According to this theory, epithelia of the female genital tract simultaneously respond to a carcinogenic stimulus.[7,8]

Perhaps those patients have a more fragile genome and prior genetic damage may predispose to the development of synchronous primary cancers of the female genital tract.[7,10-14] Thus, embryologic, hormonal or other phenomena may be associated with the development of synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers.[5-10,12]

Systematic surgical staging is the treatment of choice, for most patients with synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers[2,3,5,15-21] More specifically, systematic surgical staging in those patients includes: total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy, total omentectomy, appendectomy, pelvic and para-aortic lymphadenectomy, complete resection of all disease, biopsy of any suspected lesion and pelvic washings.[1,2,5,15-19,21-23]

It is obvious that systematic surgical staging allows a more clear decision for stage related postoperative adjuvant treatment.

[1,17,18] Appropriate surgical staging facilitates targeted therapy that minimize the morbidity of overtreatment (radiation injury, chemotherapy toxicity), the effects of undertreatment (recurrent disease, increased mortality) and maximize survival.[24]

Pelvic and para-aortic lymphadenectomy has diagnostic, therapeutic and prognostic value.[1,22,23] It defines accurately the extent of disease and determines the prognosis of patients.[1] Undoubtedly, it is necessary for the identification of patients with stage III disease. [22,23] The extension of pelvic and para-aortic lymphadenectomy (more than 14 lymph nodes) is an independent risk factor for postoperative complications.[17,18,25-27] Especially in elderly patients and in patients with relevant comorbidities (obesity, diabetes, coronary artery disease), morbidity must be carefully weighed against any survival advantage.[24,28,29]

The significance of postoperative adjuvant treatment in patients with synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers, remains controversial and needs further investigation.[16,20,30] In most cases, postoperative adjuvant treatment should be individualized according to the risk of relapse of each primary cancer. [30,31] Moreover, the treatment of one primary cancer does not compromise the treatment of the other primary cancer.[32]

Especially in patients with unfavorable histologic types, high grade and/or advanced stage disease, required postoperative adjuvant treatment tailored to both tumors.[3,5,15,17-21,30,32-36] More specifically, postoperative adjuvant treatment in those patients includes: radiotherapy and/or chemotherapy.[1,21,30,36]

Postoperative adjuvant radiotherapy includes: external pelvic radiotherapy and/or brachytherapy. It is the appropriate treatment for high risk primary endometrial cancer.[1,17,18]

Postoperative adjuvant chemotherapy is the appropriate treatment for advanced stage primary endometrial and ovarian cancers.[31] The most active chemotherapeutic agents for those patients, are: taxanes, anthracyclines and platinum compounds.[20,21]

Prognostic factors for synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers are: age, grade of endometrial cancer, stage of ovarian cancer and adjuvant treatment.[35,37,38] Patients with synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers have 5-year overall survival 85.9% and 10 year overall survival 80.3%.[16] However, patients with synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers endometrioid type have a better overall survival compared with patients with non-endometrioid or mixed histologic types. [39] Moreover, patients with synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers have better overall survival compared with patients with single primary ovarian cancer.[30,32,35,39]

The reason for the better overall survival of patients with synchronous primary endometrial and ovarian cancers, is not intuitively obvious.[16] Perhaps favorable prognosis related with the detection of patients at early stage and low grade disease.[3,5,11-13,15-34,40]

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